

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
1	14032023		Original version
2	21042023	Liese Gilles	Update contributing studies
3	05062023	Liese Gilles	Update contributing studies
4	17082023	Liese Gilles	Update contributing studies/ Contribution NIOM/WULS, contribution SZU-SK in children cancelled
5	24102023	Liese Gilles	New contribution from NIOM, NPHC, RIVM (adults). Cancelled contribution from SK, IL (children)
6	08012024	Liese Gilles	New contribution from Sweden in teenagers.

P4.1.1.1_Y1_GenHBMSurvey selection of contributing studies

Context of P4.1.1.1_Y1_GenHBMSurvey

Concept - Towards a harmonized HBM program/survey for Europe.

Within PARC, it has been decided to build on existing HBM initiatives in the countries/regions, as done within HBM4EU, instead of setting up a European HBM program that is 100% harmonized, with 1 study protocol to be applied by all countries, such as in the DEMOCOPHES project. This because within PARC the largest financial contribution must come from the countries (55%) and the EU funding is limited (45%).

In continuation of HBM4EU Aligned studies...

From the lessons learnt in HBM4EU, some improvements will be implemented in comparison with the HBM4EU Aligned Studies (Gilles et al. 2021). A shorter sampling period is selected: a 3-year sampling period (1 May 2023 – 30 April 2026) to allow synchronized sampling one year after the start of PARC. This should allow the adoption of harmonized questionnaires, protocols for sampling, consent forms, etc. Also, the selected substance groups should be measured in all studies, allowing to further explore mixture exposure. Moreover, exclusion criteria were established for local studies or studies not targeting the general population (e.g., voluntary study among students, study only recruiting men or women...).

Objectives of the PARC Aligned Studies

1. To obtain HBM (Human Biomonitoring) data, which are comparable between EU countries/regions.

Important for this objective is harmonization of the studies in all study phases + to collect a general population sample that is representative for pre-defined criteria (sex, degree of urbanization, SES) in 3 age groups.

2. To calculate European Exposure values on a pooled EU dataset

European exposure values are “indicator” values which can be compared with international chemical monitoring programmes such as NHANES (National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey; US, CDC), KoNEHS (Korean National Environmental Health Survey; Korea), CHMS (Canadian Health Measures Survey; Canada) or compared to data from previous EU projects (DEMOCOPHES, HBM4EU). For this purpose, it is important to have a broad common set of markers analysed in all contributing studies to have good EU wide coverage in exposure data.

3. To identify exposure determinants on a pooled EU dataset.

Pooling data from countries together gives a larger dataset and results in more statistical power to enable identification of exposure determinants. Important for this goal is harmonization of auxiliary information collected through questionnaires. Determinants include (socio-economic factors, or use patterns, behavioral aspects...)

4. To study exposure - effect associations.

The collection of health outcome information (optional) and analysis of selected effect biomarkers (optional) to evaluate a priori defined exposure-effect hypothesis.

All these results serve to support policy processes regarding chemicals management and regulation.

Flowchart of the selection process

- National level HBM surveys are preferred. Regional HBM surveys can only contribute when a national survey is lacking, and other criteria are fulfilled.
- Local studies are excluded.
- Studies need to fulfill certain quality criteria to be eligible.
 - **Gender:** Include participants of both gender in a 50:50 ratio
 - **Age range:** preferably each contributing study covers the complete age range, in case of strong deviation, case-by-case evaluation on contribution.
 - **SES/ISCED¹:** Preferably each participating study should approach national or regional statistics for ISCED.
 - **DEGURBA²:** Preferably each contributing study approaches national (or regional) statistics for degree of urbanization. Each of the 3 levels of urbanization should be represented at least 10% (with the exception to go <10% for a specific level if this is in line with the real situation in the country or region the sample is representing).
- Sample size restriction for countries/regions with less than 3 NUTS 3 areas -> max. co-funded sample size N = 150³.
- Geographical distribution/spread of sample collection in relation to fieldwork feasibility. Per N = 50 a different NUTS3 area must be included⁴.
- Sample size: Minimal contribution with N = 150, max sample size to receive co-fund N = 300.

¹ ISCED = International Standard Classification of Education by UNESCO.

² DEGURBA = degree of urbanisation by EUROSTAT

³ This follows the approach of DEMOCOPHES <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1408616>. *The cross-sectional survey was designed to include 120 children (5–11years of age) and their mothers in each country, with 60 mother–child pairs each in Cyprus and Luxembourg because of the countries' smaller populations.*

⁴ Exception for Luxembourg and Cyprus only 1 NUTS 3 area is defined, for Iceland only 2 NUTS3 areas are defined.

Studies approved for inclusion in the General survey

Children

- UK (new national HBM campaign) by UKHSE
!participation at 100% own financing
- Denmark (School survey) by RegionH
!sample size co-fund limitation -> N = 150, only 3 NUTS 3 areas covered
- Latvia (new national HBM) by RSU
- Estonia (new national HBM) by University Tartu/ health board
- Poland (new national HBM campaign) by WULS
- Czech Republic (National HBM campaign) by SZU-CZ (NIPH)
- Hungary (new national HBM campaign) by NPHC
- ~~Slovakia (new national HBM campaign) by SZU~~
!Study design limitation: age coverage limited and on upper limit (i.e., only 11-year-old individuals), accept this limitation as otherwise there is no contribution/representation from SK. Update: timing uncertain "It seems that the national HBM will not be launched in a close future (within 2-3 years)"
Update: cancelled for PARC, it will not be possible to implement the study within the project's timing.
- Spain (new national HBM campaign) by ISCIII
- Portugal (new national HBM campaign) by INSA
- Greece (Follow-up HBM study) by AUTH
- Slovenia (national HBM II campaign) by JSI/NIJZ
!sample size co-fund limitation -> N = 150, only 3 NUTS 3 areas covered
- Cyprus (new national HBM campaign) by MOH-CY/SGL
!sample size co-fund limitation -> N = 150
- Germany (new national HBM campaign) by UBA
- France (ALBANE) by SPF
- Austria (national HBM monitoring study) by EAA
- Luxembourg (new national HBM campaign) by LNS
!sample size co-fund limitation -> N = 150
- ~~Israel (new national HBM campaign) by MOH-IL~~
Update: cancelled due to budget cuts.

Teenagers

- UK (new national HBM campaign) by UKHSE
!participation at 100% own financing
- Denmark (School survey) by RegionH
!sample size co-fund limitation -> N = 150, only 3 NUTS 3 areas covered
- Norway (NEB III, Norwegian Environmental Biobank) by NIPH
- Latvia (new national HBM) by RSU
- Poland (new national HBM campaign) by NIOM
- Slovenia (national HBM II campaign) by JSI/NIJZ
!sample size co-fund limitation -> N = 150, only 3 NUTS 3 areas covered
- Greece (Follow-up HBM study) by AUTH
- Portugal (new national HBM campaign) by INSA
- Belgium (FLEHS V, Flemish region HBM campaign) by VITO/PIH/DOMG
- Germany (new national HBM campaign) by UBA
- France (ALBANE) by SPF
- ~~Switzerland (New national cohort study (Schweizer Gesundheitsstudie)) by FOPH/Unisanté~~
!participation at 100% own financing. Update: the Swiss HBM study has been postponed to after 2025, so that unfortunately we will not be able to take part.
- Update: Sweden (Time trend study every 4th year in south region of Sweden, expanded to cover all NUTS1 regions) by KI, UmU, ULUND.
- Update: Slovakia (pending - to be confirmed)

Adults

- UK (new national HBM campaign) by UKHSE
!participation at 100% own financing
- Lithuania (national HBM study combined with HES) by LSMU
- Latvia (new national HBM) by RSU
- Estonia (new national HBM) by University Tartu/ health board
- Iceland (New HBM and follow-up from HBM4EU) by UI
!sample size co-fund limitation N = 150
- Norway (NEB III: Norwegian Environmental Biobank) by NIPH
- Czech Republic (National HBM campaign) by SZU-CZ (NIPH)
- Portugal (new national HBM campaign) by INSA
- Spain (regional representative biomonitoring program link to the Andalusian health survey) by EASP
!sample size co-fund limitation (N = 150) -> combined contribution with UPV/EHU
- Spain (regional representative biomonitoring program link to the Basque Country health survey) by UPV/EHU
!sample size co-fund limitation (N = 150) -> Combined contribution with EASP
- Cyprus (new national HBM campaign) by MOH-CY/SGL
!sample size co-fund limitation N = 150
- Italy (HBM study for PFAS RVs) by ISS
- Greece (Follow-up HBM study) by AUTH
- Belgium (BMH-Wal 1) by ISSeP
- France (ALBANE) by SPF
- Germany (GerES VI) by UBA
- ~~Switzerland (New national cohort study (Schweizer Gesundheitsstudie)) by FOPH/Unisanté~~
!participation at 100% own financing
Update: the Swiss HBM study has been postponed to after 2025, so that unfortunately we will not be able to take part.
- Luxembourg (new national HBM campaign) by LNS
!sample size co-fund limitation N = 150
- Update: The Netherlands (National Study on PFAS) by RIVM
Commitment to analyze PFAS and metals, reduced budget.
- Israel (new national HBM campaign) by MOH-IL
- Update: Hungary (new national HBM campaign) by NPHC
- Update: Poland (new national HBM campaign) by NIOM

Studies with sample size limitations because of ≤ 3 NUTS 3 areas covered

Denmark (School survey in children and teenagers) by RegionH

NUTS 1	NUTS 2		NUTS 3		Population represented by region
NUTS1: 1/1	NUTS2: 1/5	inhabitants	NUTS3: 3/11	inhabitants ⁵	
DK0			Byen København DK011	799.033	
			Københavns omegn DK012	550.504	
			Bornholm DK013	465.887	
	Hovedstaden (DK01)	1.855.084	...		
...				1.815.424	31.09%

The area covered by the study represents 1.815.424 inhabitants. Which represents 31.09% of DK population. Geographical distribution 3 NUTS 3 regions are covered. Following the decision tree, it means they can contribute with N = 150 for which co-fund in PARC can be provided, as they only cover 3 NUTS3 areas.

Slovenia (national HBM II campaign children and teenagers) by JSI/NIJZ

NUTS 1	NUTS 2		NUTS 3		Population represented by region
NUTS1: 1/1	NUTS2: 2/2	inhabitants	NUTS3: 3/12	Inhabitants ⁵	
SI0	Zahodna Slovenija (SI04)	1.003.931	Obalno-kraska (Coastal area) SI044	118.389	
			Goriska (Idrija and Soča river catchment) SI043	118.525	
				
	Vzhodna Slovenija (SI03)	1.105.046	Jugozvhodna Slovenija (Bela Krajina) SI037	145.923	
				382.837
					18.15%

⁵ Source (EUROSTAT): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/DEMO_R_PJANGRP3_custom_4577632/default/table?lang=en

The remaining areas to be sampled within the national Slovenian HBM survey represents 382.837 inhabitants. Which represents 18.15% of SI population. Following the decision tree, it means they can contribute with N = 150 for which co-fund in PARC can be provided, as only 3 NUTS 3 regions are covered.

Cyprus (new national HBM campaign)

Cyprus has 896.005 inhabitants and only 1 NUTS 3 area -> maximal contribution for which co-fund in PARC can be provided limited to N = 150.

Iceland (New HBM and follow-up from HBM4EU) by UI

Iceland has 368.792 inhabitants and only 2 NUTS 3 areas -> maximal contribution for which co-fund in PARC can be provided limited to N = 150.

Luxembourg (new national HBM campaign) by LNS

Luxembourg has 634.730 inhabitants and only 1 NUTS 3 area -> maximal contribution for which co-fund in PARC can be provided limited to N = 150.

Studies excluded for the General survey

Local studies

Sweden (Time trend study on metals in children and 4-annual time trends study in teenagers) by ULUND

NUTS 1	NUTS 2		NUTS 3	inhabitants	Population represented by region
NUTS1: 1/3	NUTS2: 1/8		NUTS3: 1/21		
SE2	Sydsverige SE22		Skane County SE224	1.389.336	13.39%
			...		
	...				

Geographical distribution too limited, only 1 NUTS 3 area covered.

The study in children (Landskrona even 1 city area within Skane County SE224).

Denmark (RHINESSA follow-up, adults) by AU

NUTS 1	NUTS 2		NUTS 3	inhabitants	Population represented by region
NUTS 1: 1/1	NUTS2: 1/5	inhabitants	NUTS3: 1/11		
DK0	Midtjylland (DK04)		Vestjylland DK041		
			Østjylland DK042	903.974	15.48%
	...				

Geographical distribution too limited, only 1 NUTS 3 area covered. (Aarhus even 1 city area within Østjylland DK042).

Regional studies when a national alternative study is available

Czech Republic (CELSPAC: TNG – children) by MU

For Czech Republic in children a national level HBM study performed by NIPH is selected.

Spain (HBM in children follow-up of birth cohort) by IDAEA-CSIC and FINBA

For Spain in children a national level HBM study performed by ISCIII is selected.

Czech Republic (CELSPAC YA – adults) by MU

For Czech Republic in adults a national level HBM study performed by NIPH is selected.

Spain (INMA-Granada cohort) by UGR

For Spain no national level HBM study available. 2 Regional studies have proposed a combined participation (1. regional representative biomonitoring program link to the Basque Country health survey. + 2. Regional representative biomonitoring program link to the Andalusian health survey (AHS)). The INMA cohort represents a smaller region within Andalusia.

Studies with study design limitations

Finland (HealthyFinland) by THL (Candidate withdrawn)

It is not possible to share the pseudonymized individual level data that effectively prevents THL from participating to PARC with our HealthFinland-2023 material.

The protocol and questionnaires were not prepared so that they could have been included in our Healthy Finland study within our schedule.

Other

Finland (Northern Finland Birth cohort, follow-up) by University of Oulu (Candidate withdrawn)

Update: We have in UOULU checked all possibilities to collect 150 – 300 sub-study based on NFBC 1985/1986 before the cohort members will be over aged (> 39 years), and it is not possible.

Overview of the selected studies

Following the decision tree in the selection process results in following overview:

Children

North (20%)			East (17%)			South (26%)			West (37%)		
Country/Partner	Sample size		Country/ Partner	Sample size		Country/ Partner	Sample size		Country/ Partner	Sample size	
UK	UKHSE	150	PL	WULS	200-300	ES	ISCIII	300	DE	UBA	300
DK	RegionH	<u>150</u>	CZ	SZU-CZ	150-200	PT	INSA	300	FR	SPF	300
LV	RSU	200	HU	NPHC	300	EL	AUTH	150-300	AT	EAA	200
EE	University Tartu/ Health Board	150-200				SI	JSI	<u>150</u>	LU	LNS	<u>150</u>
						CY	MOH-CY/SGL	<u>150</u>			
Target:	2	600	2	600		3	900		4	1200	
Sum:	4	650-700	3	650-800		5	1050-1200		4	950	
Total:	16 studies, sample size: 3300-3650.										

Teenagers

	North (20%)			East (17%)			South (26%)			West (37%)		
	Country/Partner		Sample size	Country Partner		Sample size	Country Partner		Sample size	Country Partner		Sample size
	UK	UKHSE	150	PL	NIOM	200-300	SI	JSI	<u>150</u>	DE	UBA	300
	DK	RegionH	<u>150</u>				EL	AUTH	300	FR	SPF	300
	NO	NIPH	200				PT	INSA	300	BE	VITO/PIH	300
	LV	RSU	200									
	SE	KI, UmU, ULUND	150									
Target:	2		600	2		600	3		900	4		1200
Sum:	4		850	<u>1</u>		200-300	3		<u>750</u>	3		<u>900</u>
Total:	12 studies (1 gap East), sample size: 2700-2800											

Adults

North (20%)			East (17%)			South (26%)			West (37%)			Outside Europe		
Country/Partner		Sample size	Country/Partner		Sample size	Country/Partner		Sample size	Country/Partner		Sample size	Country/Partner		Sample size
UK	UKHSE	150	CZ	SZU-CZ	200	ES	EASP/UPV	300	DE	UBA	300	IL	MOH-IL	150
LT	LSMU	300	PL	NIOM	300	EL	AUTH	200-300	FR	SPF	300			
LV	RSU	300	HU	NPHC	150	PT	INSA	300	BE	ISSeP	300			
EE	University Tartu/Health Board	150-200				CY	MOH-CY/SGL	<u>150</u>	LU	LNS	<u>150</u>			
IS	UI	<u>150</u>				IT	ISS	300	NL	RIVM	150-300			
NO	NIPH	200												
Target:	2	600	2		600	3		900	4		1200			
Sum:	6	1250-1300	3		650	5		1250-1350	5		1200-1350	1		150
Total:	20 studies, sample size: 4500-4800													

PARC countries not contributing:

- Finland, candidate study does not fulfill requirements/criteria -> *no open slots reserved for North EU*
- Croatia, no candidate study proposed
- Slovakia, *discussions ongoing*
- Ireland, *discussions ongoing*

Involvement of 24/28 PARC participating countries.

Gaps to reach defined targets

Some gaps still need to be filled to reach the defined targets.

EU wide geographical coverage and sample size

Maximum scenario: inclusion of all EU PARC countries per age group is not feasible.

Alternative: Inclusion of a minimal number of 11 countries and minimal sample size proportionally distributed over the 4 EU regions (North, East, South, West) based on regional population size.

HBM4EU			PARC		
	EU inhabitants presented by the region compared to whole EU ⁶ (%).	Minimum N of countries to be included	EU inhabitants presented by the region, compared to whole EU ⁷ (%).	Minimal N of countries to be included (for details see annex point 1)	Target sample size to be included
North	21	2	20	2	600
East	11	1	17	2	600
South	28	2-3	26	3	900
West	40	3-4	37	4	1200
				11 countries	3300 participants

	Children	Teenagers	Adults
North			
East		A:1 open slot	A: 1 open slot
South		B:1 open slot	
West	B:1 open slot		

A: In some cases we do not reach the minimum N of studies per region:

=> Eastern Europe teenagers. -> **Initiate discussions with National Hubs from East to search for options.** Update: Possible contribution by SK in teenagers, negotiations ongoing

=> Western Europe teenagers. -> no options.

B: In some cases we do reach the minimum N of countries per region but not the sample size target:

=> Western Europe children, Southern Europe teenagers

West: an additional study in children needed to reach the sample size target.

⁶ To calculate the proportional % per region, only the HBM4EU participating countries were considered as reference for EU.

⁷ To calculate the proportional % per region, EU-27 + UK + NO + IS + CH were used as reference for EU. Calculations are based on EUROSTAT data: population size January 1st, 2021, but for the UK we used population size of January 1st, 2020 as statistics for 2021 were not available.

https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=demo_pjan&lang=en

East: an additional study in teenagers needed to reach the target of min N countries and sample size target.

South: an additional study in teenagers needed to reach sample size target.

Based on the current selection of studies following limitations are identified:

- Not all EU or PARC participating countries have national level HBM studies. Therefore, the General Survey will consist of a mix of nationally representative HBM surveys and regionally representative HBM surveys. On the long-term national level implementation of HBM will be further encouraged in the frame of a sustainable HBM programme for Europe.
- Different study designs are combined (e.g., cross sectional surveys, follow-up of longitudinal cohorts, HBM combined with HES or nutritional surveys).
- Not all studies will cover the full age range of the selected age groups of children (6-11y), teenagers (12-17y) and adults (18-39y). This implies that one has to be careful comparing results between studies as. As such, age should be adjusted for in statistical models when analysing the data.
- The studies all collect samples between May 2023-April 2026, however the individual studies do not cover the full time range as a result there will be some studies that sample e.g. in 2023-2024 only and other may sample 2025-2026. So there will be some time differences between the individual studies.
- Risk for an underrepresentation of individuals with low Socio-economic status (based on educational level attained). As participation rate of this subgroup tends to be lower.

References

Gilles, L., E. Govarts, L. Rambaud, N. Vogel, A. Castano, M. Esteban Lopez, L. Rodriguez Martin, G. Koppen, S. Remy, M. Vrijheid, P. Montazeri, L. Birks, O. Sepai, L. Stewart, U. Fidicke, I. Loots, L. E. Knudsen, M. Kolossa-Gehring, and G. Schoeters. 2021. 'HBM4EU combines and harmonises human biomonitoring data across the EU, building on existing capacity - The HBM4EU survey', *Int J Hyg Environ Health*, 237: 113809.